

RESEARCH ARTICLE

REVISED **Synthesis and physical characteristics of narrow bandgap chalcogenide SnZrSe₃ [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]**

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Abstract

Background: The development of organic/inorganic metal halide perovskites has seen unprecedented growth since their first recognition for applications in optoelectronic devices. However, their thermodynamic stability and toxicity remains a challenge considering wide-scale deployment in the future. This spurred an interest in search of perovskite-inspired materials which are expected to retain the advantageous material characteristics of halide perovskites, but with high thermodynamic stability and composed of earth-abundant and low toxicity elements. ABX₃ chalcogenides (A, B=metals, X=Se, S) have been identified as potential class of materials meeting the aforementioned criteria.

Methods: In this work, we focus on studying tin zirconium selenide (SnZrSe₃) relevant physical properties with an aim to evaluate its prospects for application in optoelectronics. SnZrSe₃ powder and monocrystals were synthesized via solid state reaction in 600 – 800 °C temperature range. Crystalline structure was determined using single crystal and powder X-ray diffraction methods. The bandgap was estimated from diffused reflectance measurements on powder samples and electrical properties of crystals were analysed from temperature dependent *I-V* measurements.

Results: We found that SnZrSe₃ crystals have a needle-like structure (space group – *Pnma*) with following unit cell parameters: *a*=9.5862(4) Å, *b*=3.84427(10) Å, *c*=14.3959(5) Å. The origin of the low symmetry crystalline structure was associated with stereochemical active electron lone pair of Sn cation. Estimated bandgap was around 1.15

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eV which was higher than measured previously and predicted theoretically. Additionally, it was found that resistivity and conductivity type depended on the compound chemical composition.

Conclusions: Absorption edge in the infrared region and bipolar dopability makes SnZrSe_3 an interesting material candidate for application in earth-abundant and non-toxic single/multi-junction solar cells or other infrared based optoelectronic devices.

Keywords

ABX₃ chalcogenides, crystal structure, optoelectronic properties, bandgap

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REVISED Amendments from Version 1

The new version of the publication entails:

1. Updated Figure 1 (XRD patterns) and complemented paragraph about solid state reaction and XRD analysis. More experimental evidence were provided on how to obtain higher yield of SnZrSe₃ phase.
2. Update on experimental details covering new experiment parameters.
3. Where relevant, elaborated discussions regarding the SnZrSe₃ optical properties with respect to its non-perovskite structure.
4. Added three new references.

Any further responses from the reviewers can be found at the end of the article

Plain language summary

The sun provides an enormous amount of energy to the planet and has the potential to meet all humanity power demands. Photovoltaic (PV) technologies, i.e. devices that convert sunlight directly to electricity, play an essential role in harvesting this solar energy. While the sun will shine and provide clean energy for many million years to come, the manufacture of PV technologies uses finite earth resources and depending on the type of technology can be energy demanding and therefore emit large amounts of CO₂. For these reasons, scientists are constantly improving synthesis and fabrication processes to increase material utilization, improving device structure to increase power conversion coefficient and study stability dynamics to prolong device lifetime. In parallel, new materials composed of earth-abundant and non-toxic chemical elements are explored which could potentially replace or complement current technologies. In this work, we focus on investigating a promising compound composed of non-toxic and earth-abundant elements from ABX₃ chalcogenide family materials – SnZrSe₃. Using a solid state reaction method, we synthesized SnZrSe₃ crystals and measured their optical and electrical properties. We found that a critical semiconductor feature – bandgap (which indicates what wavelength light will be absorbed) of SnZrSe₃ is in the suitable range for application in solar cells. Additionally, electrical measurements indicated that SnZrSe₃ can be engineered to behave as n- or p-type semiconductor which is very important for the formation of semiconductor devices. In summary, we believe that SnZrSe₃ is an interesting candidate for development of greener PV technologies.

Introduction

Perovskite class of materials describe compounds sharing the same type of crystal structure (perovskite) and have specific stoichiometry – ABX₃, where A and B are cations, and X is an anion. The unprecedented development of organic/inorganic lead halide perovskites (HP) for application in light-emitting diodes¹, X-ray detectors² and photovoltaics³ has been witnessed in the last decade. Despite their tremendous success, poor thermodynamic stability under ambient conditions⁴ and the presence of a toxic chemical element (Pb)⁵ question their wide-scale deployment in the future. This spurred an interest in search of materials with the same advantageous physical properties as HP,

but with much higher chemical stability and environmentally benign compositions⁶.

The success of HP is thought to be caused by an unusual material property – defect tolerance. This means that despite having a high density of crystallographic defects in the semiconductor, charge carrier lifetime on the order of μs can be readily obtained⁷. However, there is no consensus on the origins of the defect tolerance and it has been associated with multiple material aspects that are characteristic to metal HP, such as: special bonding-antibonding character when antibonding states are at the top of the valence band⁸, coordination environment and ionic nature of chemical bonds^{6,9}, and with a high static dielectric constant effectively screening charged defects^{6,10}.

When searching for perovskite-inspired materials it is therefore important to know how defect tolerance is related to the structural characteristics of the compound. For instance, it has been proposed that materials comprised of cations with lone electron pairs can potentially have defect tolerance characteristics¹⁰. Alternatively, a more straightforward way is to explore compounds with perovskite structure and ABX₃ composition. For this reason, and because of high thermodynamic stability, low toxicity and earth-abundant chemical composition, chalcogenide perovskites (X=Se, S) have gained a lot of interest in recent years¹¹.

The first study on chalcogenide perovskite properties using first-principles calculations was introduced by Sun *et al.*¹² (Note: that the study was limited to chalcogenide composition A²⁺B⁴⁺X²⁻₃, where A=Ca, Sr, Ba; B=Ti, Zr; Hf, X=Se, S). It was shown that chalcogenide perovskites had photovoltaic-relevant properties and some even exceeded well-established materials used in solar cells, showing their great potential in photovoltaics. This sparked an interest in chalcogenide perovskites, of which BaZrS₃ has drawn the most attention¹³⁻¹⁶. It was, however, shown that among many ABX₃ chalcogenides, under normal conditions, only very few exist as perovskite structures¹⁷: BaZrS₃, BaHfS₃, SrZrS₃, SrHfS₃, CaZrS₃. All of them are wide bandgap (> 1.7 eV) semiconductors, and therefore have a relatively narrow application range in optoelectronics. Other ABX₃ chalcogenides although in a non-perovskite ground phase have bandgaps spanning from near to mid-wavelength infrared regions¹². Additionally, because valence and conduction bands in edge(face)-sharing ABX₃ chalcogenides are primarily determined by p and d orbitals of X and B elements, respectively, the absorption coefficient is expected to be high as well¹⁸. Note, however, that lower symmetry crystal structures such as needle-like or BaNiO₃ type can lead to indirect optical transitions and therefore higher absorption onset as compared with ABX₃ chalcogenides in perovskite-type structure.

In this work, we focus on examining SnZrSe₃ which is predicted to have a narrow ~ 0.65 eV bandgap¹⁹. SnZrSe₃ is composed of low-toxicity and earth-abundant chemical elements and is stable under ambient conditions. Additionally, SnZrSe₃ and SnZrS₃ are both stable in the needle-like phase suggesting

a full chemical range of miscibility in $\text{SnZrSe}_x\text{S}_{3-x}$ alloy and therefore a high tuneability of the bandgap. Experimentally estimated bandgaps for SnZrSe_3 and SnZrS_3 were 0.86 eV and 1.2 – 1.4 eV, respectively, however, the data are available only from one source²⁰. Therefore, herein we aim to synthesize and estimate the optical and electrical properties of SnZrSe_3 for potential application in infrared-based optoelectronic devices.

SnZrSe_3 was synthesized by solid state reaction in a powder form and as monocrystals. SnZrSe_3 was found to crystallize in orthorhombic structure with space group $Pnma$ as confirmed by single-crystal and powder diffraction methods. The absorption edge was estimated at around 1.15 eV indicating to the narrow bandgap nature of SnZrSe_3 , but considerably higher than reported before and predicted theoretically. Finally, depending on the chemical composition, SnZrSe_3 was found to behave as an n - or p -type semiconductor highlighting bipolar dopability in SnZrSe_3 compound.

Methods

SnZrSe_3 samples were synthesized via a solid state reaction method. Elemental precursors comprising Sn (99.995%, AlfaAesar, -100 mesh), Zr (99.5% STREM Chemicals, -50 mesh), Se (99.999%, AlfaAesar, -200 mesh) and SnI_2 (99.99%, SigmaAldrich, -10 mesh) were weighted in an Ar filled glove box. The total mass of the precursor before annealing was 0.5 ± 0.005 g plus 0.01 ± 0.005 g of SnI_2 . Then, the precursors were introduced to a quartz ampoule (inner diameter – 8 mm, outer – 10 mm, length – 150 mm) which was capped to protect the precursors from the ambient environment when taken outside the glovebox. Before sealing, all 16 ampoules were degassed for 30 – 60 min under approximately 2 Pa pressure. Four ampoules were immersed in an ultrasonic bath to remove precursors stuck to the quartz walls. Ampoules were sealed under vacuum using a flame from an oxygen and propane gas mixture and the final ampoule length was in the 60 – 80 mm range. First batch of ampoules had a carbonized inner wall to avoid quartz reaction with precursor materials during the synthesis step. However, we did not observe any traces of chemical reactions of precursors with a quartz ampoule and the carbonization step was not used for the rest of the samples.

Ampoules were introduced in the tube furnace, 13 of them in a horizontal and 3 of them in a vertical (placed in ceramic holder) positions at the centre of the heating zone. The heating process included either one or two steps: (i) temperature was raised to the top temperature within 3 – 7 h which was varied in the 600 – 800 °C range and held for 10 – 80 h; (ii) in the second step, the temperature was reduced to 100 – 600 °C within 7 – 60 h, and furnace power was switched off leaving to cool down naturally for a few hours. We found that larger crystals were formed when the temperature was reduced slowly in the second stage, instead of maintaining a high furnace temperature for a prolonged period of time.

Single crystal X-ray data of SnZrSe_3 were obtained at 20 °C using an Xcalibur E diffractometer equipped with an Eos CCD

space detector (Agilent Technologies) and a monochromatic source of MoK_α radiation (graphite monochromator, Oxford inst.). The data were collected and processed using the program *CrysAlisPro* (Oxford Diffraction Ltd., Version 1.171.37.35, provided with diffractometer) and were corrected for the Lorentz and polarization effects, and absorption. All calculations to solve the structures and to refine the proposed models were carried out with the *SHELXS97*²¹ and *SHELXL2014* software packages²² (*SHELX* is free of charge for academic users).

The structure was refined by the full matrix least squares method on F2 with anisotropic displacement parameters using the program *SHELXL*²¹. Crystallographic data and structure refinement details and geometric parameters are given in CIF file (see *Underlying data*²³). CIF files were deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre CCDC/ICSD, deposition number CSD 2166561, and can be accessed upon request (<https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/>).

Powder diffraction was measured using Rigaku diffractometer SmartLab with 9 kW rotating Cu anode in Bragg-Brentano geometry. Before measurements, crystals collected from the ampoule were grinded in an agate mortar. Diffractograms were recorded in the range of 10 to 60 2 θ degrees with a scan step of 0.01 degree using linear D/tex ultra detector.

Raman measurements were performed using an inVia Raman microscope (Renishaw, Wotton-under Edge, UK) equipped with the 1800 lines/mm grating and thermoelectrically cooled (-70 °C) CCD camera at 532 nm wavelength excitation. Raman spectrum was taken using a 50x/0.75 NA (Leica) objective lens. Laser power was restricted to 0.05 mW and the integration time was set to 300 s. The Raman frequencies were calibrated using the silicon standard according to the line at 520.7 cm^{-1} .

Diffuse reflectance was measured using Shimadzu UV-3600 two-beam spectrometer equipped with a multi-purpose compartment MPC-3100. Samples were placed in a 60 mm integrating sphere and a barium sulphate target was used for calibration.

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) images were taken using Helios Nanolab 650 equipped with a field emission gun. Chemical composition was recorded with an energy dispersive spectrometer (Oxford inst.) embedded in SEM. Before Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) measurements were made, calibration using a Cu plate was performed and other parameters such as working distance (5 mm), accelerating voltage (20 kV) and exposure time (30s) were kept constant.

Temperature dependent current-voltage measurements were recorded using a Keithley 6487 picoammeter/voltage source. The sample was placed in a closed helium cycle cryostat (Janis CCS-100/204) and the temperature was controlled via a digital temperature controller. Current-voltage measurements were made from 295 to 100 K with a 10 K temperature step size.

Once the set temperature was reached on the thermocouple, it was waited for 3 min for temperature to equalize on the sample.

All data visualization and processing were performed using OriginPro 2021 version 9.8.0.200 (<https://www.originlab.com/index.aspx?go=Products/Origin>) and files are accessible in *Underlying data*²³. Alternatively, data can be treated and analysed using freely available software Labplot (<https://labplot.kde.org/>). Visualization of crystalline structure was done using freely available software Mercury (<https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/solutions/csd-core/components/mercury/>).

Results

SnZrSe₃ solid state synthesis

SnZrSe₃ was synthesized via solid state reaction from precursors in elemental form. Unless stated otherwise, a transport agent (SnI₂) was used to accelerate the reaction and to grow single crystals. In other cases, no additives were introduced. In most of experiments, various shapes, sizes and forms of crystals were present inside an ampoule after annealing indicating formation of secondary phases. By analysing X-ray diffraction (XRD) data we found that in addition to SnZrSe₃ phase, one or two of the following binary phases were present:

ZrSe₃ (ICDD# 03-065-2351), ZrSe₂ (ICDD# 04-005-5128) and SnSe (ICDD# 04-009-2257). Based on multiple trials, we noticed that the following experimental parameters had a deciding factor on the phase composition: (i) spatial separation of precursor materials (ii) Se overpressure in the ampoule and (iii) annealing duration. When the ampoule was oriented vertically in the annealing zone, ZrSe₃ and traces of SnSe phases were present despite the annealing temperature applied (Figure 1a). Interestingly, the addition of transport agent in a form of SnI₂ did not change the phase composition. This suggested that when precursors were in close proximity, the solid-state reaction was not accelerated or favoured for the formation of SnZrSe₃ in the presence of a transport agent. When ampoules were oriented horizontally and precursor powder was spread over a certain length, phase composition strongly depended on the initial Se content. Using Se-deficient precursor, a large amount of ZrSe₂ and absence of ZrSe₃ phases were observed in the powder (Figure 1b). Once stoichiometric or Se-rich precursors were used, little to no amount of ZrSe₂ was found, which indicated that the formation of ZrSe₃ phase was highly favoured under Se-rich atmosphere. Note that when the ampoules were oriented horizontally no secondary Sn-related phases were observed. Finally, the annealing duration at the top temperature had a significant effect on

Figure 1. Phase composition analysis determined by X-ray diffraction method. (a) Diffractograms of SnZrSe₃ powder synthesized at various temperatures in a vertical position without and with transport agent. (b) Diffractograms of SnZrSe₃ powder samples synthesized in the same experiment at 740 °C temperature in a horizontal position with different initial Se-content in the precursor as indicated in the graph. (c) Diffractograms of SnZrSe₃ powder annealed for different durations. Top temperature – 700 °C, SnI₂ transport agent, position – horizontal, precursor composition - stoichiometric. (d) XRD pattern of collected and grinded crystals synthesized at 700 °C in horizontal position with a transport agent. Diffractogram of pure SnZrSe₃ phase was simulated using CIF file (*underlying data*²³).

SnZrSe₃ powder phase purity. In the initial experiments we used long annealing durations to facilitate a complete solid-state reaction. However, we noticed that shorter annealing durations yielded lower concentration of secondary phases (Figure 1c). In the samples annealed under identical conditions but with different durations, we found that almost pure-phase powder was obtained annealing for 35 h instead of 60 h or more used previously (Figure 1c). Longer or shorter than 35 h annealing durations resulted in the formation of ZrSe₂ phase which concentration was much higher in the sample synthesized for a long period of time. This suggested that SnZrSe₃ formed relatively quickly and under prolonged annealing time slowly decomposed into binary phases. Therefore, from these results we can infer that 700 °C is close to the decomposition temperature of SnZrSe₃.

Based on the obtained results we propose a simplified reaction mechanism described below. During the temperature ramp in the synthesis process, it is suggested that SnSe is formed first, which crystallizes already at 300 °C²⁴:

where *l*, *g* and *s* indicate liquid, gaseous and solid states of matter; *x* denotes Se molecule size, which can be from 2 to 8 depending on the temperature²⁵. In parallel, Zr reacts with Se vapour and ZrSe₂ is formed as the most stable form of Zr – Se system^{26,27}:

Above 600 °C, SnSe enters a gaseous phase and starts to react with zirconium diselenide:

When there is a surplus of Se in the atmosphere, a competing reaction occurs:

Therefore, we believe that the thermodynamic balance between reactions (3) and (4) which depends on spatial separation of materials, partial Se pressure and annealing temperature determine the final product composition. While inspecting the ampoule annealed sequentially first at 700 °C and then at 800 °C, it was noticed that after the second annealing large SnZrSe₃ crystals deteriorated, and small fine needle-like crystals typical for ZrSe₃ were found (Figure S1 in *Extended data*²³). This indicated that SnZrSe₃ decomposes at higher temperatures. This observation was in agreement with the results obtained from time-dependent annealing series, where prolonged synthesis duration at 700 °C led to decomposition of SnZrSe₃. Therefore, to synthesize SnZrSe₃ phase with high yield, it is essential to keep balance between top temperature and annealing duration. With our experimental setup it was around 35 h at 700 °C. However, if lower temperature is applied, longer duration may be required and vice versa.

In this study, to obtain a pure single-phase SnZrSe₃ powder, a part of large needle-shaped crystals was collected from the ampoule's walls and was grinded in a mortar. Other crystals were used as-grown for single crystal XRD, Raman scattering and electrical measurements. The XRD pattern of thus obtained powder is presented in Figure 1d. A very good match was found between the experimental XRD pattern and the one simulated from single crystal XRD data. No traces of secondary phases were detected. Note that intensity of XRD peaks of (h0l) planes was higher than in the simulated pattern (Figure 1d). This shows that a preferred orientation of (h0l) planes was present even in the powder sample because needle-like shaped grains tend to orient with their long axis parallel to the surface. Single-phase powder was later used for optical measurements.

Determination of the SnZrSe₃ structure

To determine the crystalline structure of SnZrSe₃, needle shaped crystal with dimensions of 0.25 × 0.02 × 0.015 mm and synthesized at 700 °C was selected for single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements. The summary of crystallographic information is presented in Table 1. More details on the refinement procedure and parameters can be found in the experimental description and crystallographic information file (*Underlying data*²³) attached to the publication.

It was determined that SnZrSe₃ crystal is orthorhombic and belongs to space group *Pnma* (Figure 2a). The calculated unit cell parameters were *a* = 9.5862(4) Å, *b* = 3.84427(10) Å, *c* = 14.3959(5) Å and unit cell volume *V* = 530.52(3) Å³. The needle axis of the crystal habit corresponded to the shortest crystallographic axis *b*. The X-ray structural analysis showed that the crystalline structure of SnZrSe₃ compound was isomorphous and isostructural to the sister compound SnZrS₃²⁸. The fundamental building block of the crystalline structure was a ribbon (Figure 2b) which comprised of double edge-sharing Zr octahedra extending along *b* direction indefinitely. Within a ribbon and along *b* direction atoms are held by strong bonds as evidenced by the short interatomic distances of < 3 Å (Table 1). On the contrary, ribbons themselves are held together via van der Waals forces because of the longer interatomic distances (> 3 Å) found along directions *a* and *c* (Table 1). Within a unit cell cations occupy two non-equivalent sites Sn(1) and Zr(1), whereas anions have three distinct positions (Figure 2b). Sn(1) is coordinated with three Se atoms forming a trigonal pyramidal geometry, whereas Zr is coordinated with six Se atoms forming a distorted octahedra geometry. Additionally, the bonding environment around Sn cation in terms of bond length was found to be anisotropic (Figure 2c). Sn-Se bonds which are shorter than 3 Å are part of the ribbon structure, whereas in other directions they are longer than 3 Å giving a clear spatial separation between ribbons.

Optical characterisation of bandgap

For the optical characterization of SnZrSe₃, single-phase powder as determined from XRD measurements was selected. To examine if there were any impurity phases present on the surface of the powder, Raman scattering measurements were conducted. As seen before, XRD results showed no evidence of

Table 1. Summary of SnZrSe₃ single crystal crystallographic information.

Crystallographic information was collected using single crystal XRD method and based on SnZrSe₃ crystal synthesised at 700 °C temperature. The key information was selected.

Compound	Crystal system	Space group	Unit cell parameters		
			a, Å	b, Å	c, Å
SnZrSe ₃	Orthorhombic	<i>Pnma</i>	9.5862(4)	3.84427(10)	14.3959(5)
Atomic coordinates					
Atom	WP	x	y	x	U(eq)
Sn(1)	4c	4556(1)	7500	6664(1)	22(1)
Zr(1)	4c	1608(1)	2500	5498(1)	12(1)
Se(1)	4c	2697(1)	2500	7191(1)	16(1)
Se(2)	4c	3318(1)	7500	4876(1)	13(1)
Se(3)	4c	-155(1)	7500	6104(1)	11(1)
Geometric parameters					
Within ribbon (along <i>b</i>)		Intra ribbon (along <i>a</i>)		Inter ribbon (along <i>c</i>)	
Bond	Length, Å	Bond	Length, Å	Bond	Length, Å
Sn(1)-Se(1)	2.7291(5)	Se(2)-Se(2)	3.771	Sn(1)-Se(3)	3.225
Sn(1)-Se(2)	2.8352(7)	Sn(1)-Se(2)	3.573	Se(1)-Se(3)	3.736
Zr(1)-Se(1)	2.6514(7)				
Zr(1)-Se(2)	2.6798(5)				
Zr(1)-Se(3)	2.7041(5)				

Figure 2. Crystalline structure of needle-like SnZrSe₃ phase. Single crystal XRD results confirmed that SnZrSe₃ crystal is orthorhombic (a) The main building block of SnZrSe₃ structure is ribbon which is presented in (b) with labelled atom sites. (c) The projection of SnZrSe₃ crystal structure on (*a*, *c*) plane highlight the anisotropy around Sn cation. Dashed lines indicate > 3 Å interatomic distances in Sn coordination environment.

secondary phases (Figure 1c). For the Raman scattering study, additional samples were measured – a SnZrSe₃ monocrystal which served as a reference case. Raman spectra contained vibrational bands located at 71, 119, 133, 160, 196 and 243 cm⁻¹ (Figure 3a). Because there is no reference Raman spectrum of SnZrSe₃ in the literature, we first examined if there were secondary phases that had been observed in XRD patterns. Positions of the main and the most intensive Raman bands of ZrSe₂²⁹, SnSe³⁰ and ZrSe₃³¹ are shown as dotted lines (Figure 3a). No evidence of ZrSe₃ phase was found. However, one Raman band of SnSe (71 cm⁻¹) and three bands of ZrSe₂ (134 cm⁻¹, 196 cm⁻¹, 242 cm⁻¹) overlap very well with some of the SnZrSe₃ bands. Despite a good match, we believe it is not a response from secondary phases, but because of structural similarities between SnZrSe₃ and ZrSe₂ (SnSe) that give rise to similar vibrational bands. The main structural element in ZrSe₂ is ZrX₆ octahedral which is also the case in SnZrSe₃ (Figure 2b). Coordination environment of Sn in SnSe and SnZrSe₃ also share similar structural features therefore rendering alike Raman bands. In addition, the Raman spectrum of SnZrSe₃ monocrystal perfectly matched with Raman spectrum of the SnZrSe₃ powder sample. This strongly supports that SnZrSe₃ powder was free of secondary phases and overlapping bands were a result of similar structural characteristics between SnZrSe₃ and ZrSe₂ (SnSe).

To estimate the absorption and to calculate optical bandgap and other critical points in the electronic band, diffuse reflectance was measured of the single-phase powder sample (Figure 3b). According to the Schuster-Kubelka-Munk formulation, apparent absorption and diffuse reflection are related as follows³²:

$$F(R_{\infty}) = \frac{(1 - R_{\infty})^2}{2R_{\infty}} = \frac{K}{S} \quad (5)$$

Where, R_{∞} - diffuse reflectance, K – apparent absorption, S – reflection coefficient.

Assuming S did not change considerably over the measured energy range, $F(R_{\infty})$ was taken to reflect the SnZrSe₃

absorption coefficient. Diffused reflectance together with the calculated $F(R_{\infty})$ are depicted in Figure 3b. To estimate the bandgap, we first applied the common Tauc method³³. In brief, material's absorption coefficient (for photon energy above the bandgap) is proportional to the material's bandgap as follows: $\alpha E_{ph} \approx C(E_{ph} - E_g)^n$, where α is absorption coefficient, C – constant reflecting joint density of states in the bands, E_{ph} – is a photon energy, E_g – material's bandgap and n -exponent depending on the optical transition nature: for direct transition $n=2$, for indirect $n=0.5$. Then, to find the bandgap value, $(\alpha E_{ph})^n$ is plotted versus E_{ph} and fitted linearly. A linear fitting region is extrapolated until it crosses x axis where $\alpha \approx 0$ and the crossing point is defined as material's bandgap. Direct transition was considered for SnZrSe₃ therefore $(F(R_{\infty}) \cdot E)^2$ vs E plot was used (Figure 3b, inset). The fitted linear region near the absorption edge resulted in a bandgap value of around 1.16 eV. In the second approach, to estimate the position of critical points (CP) in the band structure, the second derivative of $F(R_{\infty})$ was calculated (Figure 3c). To reduce background noise and highlight CP features, data points were smoothed using Savitzky-Golay methods with 3rd order polynomial and a 100 point window. Note, that we did not fit the derivative with the Aspnes' function, because to obtain correct fitting results, high-accuracy measurements of material dielectric function are required. Nevertheless, the position of CP can be still estimated as the inflexion point of the CP feature, which typically has one positive and one negative extrema (Figure 3c, indicated by arrows). In addition, to validate the certainty of CPs identified in the spectrum, we calculated second derivative under various smoothing conditions for the same sample and measured the diffuse reflectance on SnZrSe₃ sample made from another batch. In all cases, inflexion points were located at the same positions (Figure S2 in Extended data²³). First, clear CP features below the SnZrSe₃ absorption edge were observed at 0.65 and 0.87 eV, respectively. The position of these CPs was in very close agreement with H₂O absorption bands which are located at 1940 nm (~0.64 eV) and 1450 nm (~0.85 eV)³⁴. This indicated that H₂O was present in BaSO₄ which was used as a white reference plate in the diffuse reflectance measurements. Such a case is quite common when BaSO₄ is used as a reference

Figure 3. Raman spectra and optical properties of SnZrSe₃ powder. (a) Raman scattering spectra of single phase SnZrSe₃ powder and monocrystal synthesized at 700°C. Excitation wavelength - 532 nm. (b) Diffuse reflectance spectrum and thereof calculated apparent absorption using eq. 5 of single-phase SnZrSe₃ powder. Inset – Tauc plot of SnZrSe₃ around absorption edge. (c) Second derivative of measured apparent absorption as a function of energy of single-phase SnZrSe₃ powder.

plate. Other CPs were located at 1.14 and 1.46 eV (Figure 3c). The low energy CP was assigned to the SnZrSe₃ bandgap because it coincided well with the value estimated from the Tauc plot (Figure 3b). However, all other higher energy CPs cannot be assigned to a specific optical transition and is beyond the scope of this work. Based on the diffuse reflectance results, SnZrSe₃ bandgap was around 1.15 eV which is almost twice as large as predicted from first-principles¹⁹ and is substantially higher than measured by Richard²⁰. First-principles calculations using hybrid potentials can predict bandgaps consistent with experimental values therefore such large discrepancy we relate to one of the two reasons: (i) SnZrSe₃ is an indirect bandgap semiconductor and using diffuse reflectance method we were not able to clearly detect weak indirect optical transitions which would be expected to be lower in energy than direct (ii) due to low density of states at the band edges, strong optical absorption starts with a high onset leading significant absorption only at higher photon energies¹⁹. The value measured by Richard was very close to the water absorption band located at 1450 nm. Although we consistently found a bandgap value of about 1.15 eV, more samples such as thin films, and other bandgap measurement methods would be useful to consolidate the real bandgap value of SnZrSe₃ and nature of transition (direct/indirect).

Electrical properties

Conductivity type is a very important factor when considering the formation of semiconductor heterojunctions. Without intentional doping, conductivity usually depends on the dominating intrinsic point defects in the material, which in turn are related to the compound stoichiometry. To study conductivity properties of SnZrSe₃, we first tested the largest needle-like crystals with a hot-point-probe method. This method allows us to identify the conductivity type by observing current/voltage sign upon increase in temperature gradient between probes. Before measurements, the system was calibrated with well-known *n*-type commercial fluorine doped SnO₂ (SigmaAldrich) sample and boron doped commercial *p*-type (100) Si wafer. It turned out that some as-grown crystals showed a constant positive voltage change upon temperature gradient increase and some – negative (Figure 4a). This indicated that SnZrSe₃ can exhibit both *n* and *p*-type conductivity. Note that *n*-type behaviour was much more pronounced suggesting higher carrier concentration was present in *n*-type than in *p*-type crystals or much higher mobility of electrons. This was also in-line with calculated resistivity which was two orders of magnitude higher for *p*-type sample (Table 2). To find if there was a relation between off-stoichiometry and conductivity type, we measured the chemical composition of crystals showing

Figure 4. Electrical properties of SnZrSe₃ crystals. (a) Voltage as a function of a temperature difference between probes measured on SnZrSe₃ crystals using hot-point-probe method. Commercial FTO (fluorine doped SnO₂) and boron doped Si wafer were used to calibrated system. (b) Electrical conductivity as a function of reciprocal temperature in three single-crystal SnZrSe₃ samples.

Table 2. Chemical composition and electrical parameters of SnZrSe₃ crystals from F1 and K1 batches. Two batches (F1 and K1) of crystals were studied which showed pronounced *n*- and *p*-type conductivity behaviour. Chemical composition clearly showed correlation with composition in uniform crystal samples.

Sample	Sn, at.%	Zr, at.%	Se, at.%	Sn/Zr	Se/(Sn+Zr)	ρ_s , $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$	E_{a1} , eV	E_{a2} , eV
<i>n</i> -F1 (HHP)	21.5±1.1	20.9±0.4	57.6±1.3	1.03	1.36			
<i>p</i> -K1 (HHP)	22.1±1.5	21.4±0.9	56.5±1.0	1.03	1.30			
F1-1	22.0±0.12	21.0±0.13	57.0±0.13	1.05	1.33	1.5·10 ³	0.28	0.22
F1-2	21.0±0.52	21.5±0.12	57.5±0.41	0.98	1.35	3.9·10 ⁴	0.24	0.20
K1-1	19.4±0.09	22.4±0.2	58.2±0.14	0.86	1.39	1.7·10 ⁵	0.39	-

n and p -type behaviour, respectively. The average composition of the crystals measured over more than 5 points are summarized in Table 2. In both samples, the cationic ratio A/B was identical, whereas the n -type crystal was slightly more Se-rich than p -type, but both were Se-deficient with respect to stoichiometric ratio of $[X]/([A]+[B])$ which is 1.5. At this point, it is difficult to confirm if the different Se quantity was the origin of respective conductivity type and would require more samples to be synthesized and tested. In addition, there was quite a large compositional variation as seen from the high standard deviation. Important to note that since iodine was used as a transport agent to facilitate the solid state reaction during synthesis, it could be inadvertently introduced in the lattice giving rise to extrinsic doping. Iodine could not be detected by EDX, but we acknowledge that very small amounts (beyond the EDX detection limit) can have a significant contribution to the conductivity behaviour. In summary, although the origin of doping is not clear in SnZrSe₃, the bipolar conductivity behaviour is a very desirable feature for semiconductor-based technologies³⁵.

To estimate the ionization potential (E_a) of defects contributing to the conductivity, temperature dependent I - V curves were measured. To avoid grain boundary effects, as monolithic as possible SnZrSe₃ samples were selected (Figure S3 in Extended data²³). However, due to their small size, their conductivity type could not be measured directly by HPP and was assumed from the measurements of larger crystals from the same batch. We found that the resistivity of samples varied in $10^3 - 10^5 \Omega\text{-cm}$ range highlighting the insulating nature of SnZrSe₃. Calculated E_a of defects are summarized in Table 2 and Figure 4b. We see that for F1 series samples two E_a were calculated, but because conductivity is the product of carrier concentration and carrier mobility, it cannot be ruled out that reduction in E_a was because of the change of carrier scattering mechanisms, and therefore increased mobility upon temperature decrease. Overall, all defects that were found to contribute to the conductivity can be considered as deep defects, because $E_a \gg 0.025 \text{ eV}$, which is a thermal excitation energy at room temperature (kT), k is Boltzmann constant and T – temperature (295 K). Chemical composition of the crystals was also measured (Table 2) to link composition with conductivity behaviour. These crystals were much more homogenous as evidenced by a small standard deviation. Notably, the specific resistance was found to correlate with the Sn/Zr ratio: the more Sn-rich sample was, the smaller resistivity. In addition, it is likely that Sn-rich composition also led to n -type conductivity, whereas Sn-deficiency – to the p -type. This would also explain why in the Sn-deficient sample (K1-1) we observed very different E_a than in the other two cases. E_a in F1 samples was related to the donor defects, whereas in K1 – to the acceptor type defects. This was not obvious when the composition of large crystals was measured because of their chemical inhomogeneity. Resistivity can also be related to the gradual change of Se content as well. However, to rely on the Se ratio to the cations is less accurate, because we found small amounts of oxygen present in the crystals, especially if exposed for a long time in the ambient environment. The oxygen is most likely

adsorbed from the air or in some amorphous state because phase composition determined by XRD of the powder sample that was stored for more than half a year under ambient conditions ($T=20\text{-}25^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH}=30\text{-}60\%$) did not change (Figure S4 in Extended data²³). This also shows high thermodynamic stability of the SnZrSe₃.

Discussion

A characteristic structural feature of perovskite compounds is that cation B forms an octahedra geometry with sharing corners³⁶. In fact, the stability of perovskite structures are predicted by estimating Goldschmidt's tolerance factor, t , which reflects an ability to squeeze octahedra in a cubic sub-lattice³⁷. However, ABX₃ chalcogenides do not follow predictions based on t only. None of the ABX₃ chalcogenides exist in a perfect cubic structure even when $t=1.0$ (which is a golden ratio for cubic perovskite). Because chalcogen ionic radius is much larger than that of oxygen, the octahedral factor (μ) must also be accounted for. Then, t is plotted against μ , it can be clearly seen that only a few ABX₃ chalcogenides fall in the region of having a perovskite structure¹⁷. For SnZrSe₃ calculated t and μ values are 0.79 and 0.36, which falls outside the perovskite region ($t > 0.85$, $\mu > 0.4$).

Instead, ABX₃ chalcogenides are found to exist in distorted perovskite (model structure – GdFeO₃), needle-like (model structure NH₄CdCl₃) and hexagonal (model structure BaNiO₃) structures. Other crystal structures also exist in ABX₃ chalcogenides, for example, CeTmS₃-type in $A^{3+}B^{3+}X^{2-}$ ³⁸, CuTaS₃-type in $A^{1+}B^{5+}X^{2-}$ ³⁹ and there are other possible variations although more rare. In needle-like and hexagonal structures, B cation octahedra is sharing edges (faces) instead of corners as is the case in SnZrSe₃ (Figure 2c). This will give rise to anisotropic carrier transport because low effective mass is expected in the direction of edge-sharing octahedra compared to other directions. Indeed, high anisotropy in electronic band dispersion was shown in SnZrS₃ and SnZrSe₃ (needle-like phase) using the first-principles calculations¹⁹.

Additionally, it is important to note the difference in bonding environment between SnZrSe₃ and other needle-like ABX₃ chalcogenides containing alkali or alkaline earth cations, for instance, SrZrSe₃ or RbCdCl₃. In SrZrSe₃, cation A is positioned almost equidistantly from the nearest neighbouring atoms⁴⁰, whereas in SnZrSe₃ as shown before there is a clear anisotropy in terms of interatomic distances (Figure 2c). The origin of the ribbon-like structure in SnZrSe₃ could be related to the stereochemically active lone electron pair. On theoretical grounds, it has been shown that stereochemically active lone pairs lead to distorted low symmetry crystal structures⁴¹. Sn in SnZrSe₃ is in a +2 valence state which leads to two unpaired 5s electrons. For the binary compounds, if there is a strong interaction between cation s states and anion p states, electronic stabilization is achieved through lattice distortion and lone electron pair is ejected outwards forming a structural void. That leads to asymmetric bonding around lone electron pair containing cation. Many chalcogenides containing cation with lone electron pair such as Sb₂Se₃, Sb₂S₃, Bi₂S₃, SnHfS₃, SnZrS₃, PbHfS₃ and PbZrS₃ have a ribbon-like low symmetry

crystal structure. Because of these structural similarities at least binary compounds also share some electronic and optical characteristics, for instance indirect bandgap with a small difference between direct and indirect gaps and anisotropic carrier transport properties⁴². Based on first-principles calculations, SnZrSe₃ is predicted to have a small (< 0.1 eV) difference between indirect and direct gaps as well¹⁹. Such characteristic is highly desired in absorber materials for photovoltaics because high absorption coefficient and long carrier lifetime can be realised simultaneously⁴². On one hand absorption coefficient (α) depends on the density of states in the bands. If states at direct gap are dispersive it can lead to slowly increasing α resulting in significant absorption onset. Based on optical properties calculated for SnZrSe₃, $\alpha > 10^4$ cm⁻¹ is reached for photon energy > 1.5 eV which renders an onset of around 0.9 eV¹⁹. Another theoretical work also shows that among ABX₃ chalcogenides those in needle-like phase have a larger absorption onset than those in perovskite structure¹², and this was measured for SrZrS₃ case experimentally⁴³. On the hand, in materials with dispersive bands, a high carrier mobility can be expected. Consequently, for practical application, for instance solar cells, an optimum absorber thickness will be required to balance between charge carrier mobility, lifetime and absorption coefficient.

In this work, we found that SnZrSe₃ showed *p* as well as *n* type conductivity behaviour. Ambipolar behaviour was also recently realised in BaZrS₃ thin films⁴⁴. This is in contrast to other multicomponent well-known Cu-based photovoltaic materials such as Cu(In,Ga)Se₂, Cu₂ZnSn(Se,S)₄, CuSb(Se,S)₂ and Cu₂Sn(Se,S)₃ where usually one type carrier is dominant. Because of low formation energy of Cu vacancy defect (acceptor type), these materials are intrinsically p-type⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸. Inability to alter the conductivity type and magnitude on demand, puts constraints on the device structure and requires formation of heterojunctions. On the contrary, if a semiconductor can be tuned to behave as *p* or *n* type, it opens up wider possibilities to design device structure, for example employing homojunctions and there is also a wider choice of partner layers for formation of heterojunctions. Bipolar dopability is therefore desired in the material because it facilitates the optimisation of device design for targeted application.

SnZrSe₃ is a promising material candidate for photovoltaic application. Nonetheless, to really highlight the potential of this material, the deposition of SnZrSe₃ in thin film form should be demonstrated and absolute values of optical absorption measured. This has not been done or reported thus far. Based on the experience in synthesis of other ABX₃ chalcogenide thin films (BaZrS₃)¹⁶, deposition process of SnZrSe₃ could be challenging. Because of the large difference in vapour pressure of constituting elements, conventional chalcogenide thin film synthesis methods can be unsuitable. Therefore, likely alternative synthesis approaches should be explored to synthesize SnZrSe₃ thin films.

Conclusions

In this work, we studied the properties of SnZrSe₃ intending to explore ABX₃ chalcogenide materials beyond the perovskite structure. We confirmed that the ground phase of SnZrSe₃ is needle-like (s.g. *Pnma*) where the main building block was a ribbon forming a quasi-one-dimensional crystal structure. Coordination anisotropy around cation A was observed in SnZrSe₃ which was a sign of a stereochemically active electron lone pair of Sn. The bandgap of SnZrSe₃ was found to be 1.15 eV which is much smaller than in perovskite chalcogenides, therefore, broadening application range of ABX₃ chalcogenides. In addition, we found that as-grown SnZrSe₃ crystals were insulating ($\rho_s = 10^3$ - 10^5 Ω -cm), showed bipolar dopability and deep intrinsic defects. In terms of ribbon-like crystal structure and optical bandgap, SnZrSe₃ has similar properties as Sb₂X₃ – which is one of the most perspective materials for earth-abundant and non-toxic photovoltaics, but SnZrSe₃ offers a wider range of tunability in terms of doping and bandgap. However, the next important step in the validation of SnZrSe₃ prospects is to find a synthesis approach for thin film deposition, which could be not as straightforward as evidenced from experience with perovskite chalcogenides.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required.

Data availability

Underlying data

Zenodo: Dataset for publication “Synthesis and physical characteristics of narrow bandgap chalcogenide SnZrSe₃”. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7867349>²³.

This project contains the following underlying data:

- Sample description.txt (synthesis conditions of the samples presented in the publication).
- FIIIS_V_6244.cif (crystallographic information file about SnZrSe₃ structure as determined by single-crystal XRD method; CIF can be opened with free of charge available software, e.g. VESTA (<https://jp-minerals.org/vesta/en/>), Mercury (<https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/solutions/csd-core/components/mercury/>)).
- XRD.zip (raw XRD patterns of powder samples presented in the publication in .ras and .raw formats; ras file can be read and plotted using open-source platform Labplot; raw/ras files can be opened and analysed in Profex (free of charge, <https://www.profex-xrd.org/>)).
- Raman.zip (raw Raman spectra in .txt format and OriginPro project file where data was plotted; alternatively, Raman spectra can also be read and plotted using open-source platform Labplot (<https://labplot.kde.org/>)).

- Optics.zip (raw diffuse reflectance data in .txt format and OriginPro project file where data was processed and plotted; diffuse reflectance spectra can also be read, analysed and plotted using open-source platform Labplot (<https://labplot.kde.org/>)).
- JV-T.zip (I-V curves at specific temperature in .txt format and OriginPro project files where data was processed and plotted; I-V data files can be read, analysed and plotted using open-source platform Labplot (<https://labplot.kde.org/>)).
- Images.zip (optical photographs of the sample and untreated SEM images of crystals).

CIF files were deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre CCDC/ICSD, deposition number CSD 2166561,

and can be accessed upon request (<https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/structures/>).

Extended data

Zenodo: Dataset for publication “Synthesis and physical characteristics of narrow bandgap chalcogenide SnZrSe₃”. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7867349>²³.

This project contains the following extended data:

- Extended data.pdf (additional information supporting claims in the publication with direct link to the main text, such as figures).

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) (CC-BY 4.0).

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Hao Zeng

Department of Physics, University at Buffalo, Buffalo, NY, USA

I am satisfied with the revised version. The manuscript is ready for indexing.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Chalcogenide perovskites, optoelectronic properties.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Version 1

Reviewer Report 22 March 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.16407.r31017>

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Yi-Yang Sun

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It is enjoyable to read through this paper, which reports the synthesis and characterization of the

compound SnZrSe_3 , an unknown material so far. Even though SnZrSe_3 appears to be isostructural to SnZrS_3 , it is an important addition to the database of inorganic crystals. The description on the experimental details and the discussion on the results are detailed and objective enough to assure the reader what has been done and what still requires further study. I have no reservation regarding the indexing of this work. Nevertheless, given the complete open nature of this journal, I would like to add a discussion which might be of interest to the readers of this paper.

The "perovskite" structure, without any generalization, should be composed of corner-shared octahedra. In this sense, the ribbon-like structure of SnZrSe_3 with edge-shared octahedra is not a perovskite. The structure difference will give rise to different electronic structures, which in turn will affect the optical absorption. While this paper measured the optical band gap, the absolute absorption coefficient was not measured. So, whether it can be suitably used for PV is still unclear. The 1.1 eV band gap is already close to the lower bound of the optimal range for a single-junction solar cell. If the fundamental gap is significantly lower than the optical band gap, it will limit the open circuit voltage to a low value.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: First-principles calculations, Raman spectrum

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Author Response 18 May 2023

Rokas Kondrotas

Reviewer #2

It is enjoyable to read through this paper, which reports the synthesis and characterization of the compound SnZrSe₃, an unknown material so far. Even though SnZrSe₃ appears to be isostructural to SnZrS₃, it is an important addition to the database of inorganic crystals. The description on the experimental details and the discussion on the results are detailed and objective enough to assure the reader what has been done and what still requires further study. I have no reservation regarding the indexing of this work. Nevertheless, given the complete open nature of this journal, I would like to add a discussion which might be of interest to the readers of this paper.

Reviewer: The "perovskite" structure, without any generalization, should be composed of corner-shared octahedra. In this sense, the ribbon-like structure of SnZrSe₃ with edge-shared octahedra is not a perovskite. The structure difference will give rise to different electronic structures, which in turn will affect the optical absorption. While this paper measured the optical band gap, the absolute absorption coefficient was not measured. So, whether it can be suitably used for PV is still unclear. The 1.1 eV band gap is already close to the lower bound of the optimal range for a single-junction solar cell. If the fundamental gap is significantly lower than the optical band gap, it will limit the open circuit voltage to a low value.

Authors: we thank the reviewer for positive feedback and raising awareness. The ideas that are expressed are very important and deserves a discussion. While providing a response to reviewer #1, some of the concerns have been discussed, and is added in the version 2 of the paper. In particular, the following discussion have been added to account for change in optical properties with respect to crystal structure: On one hand, absorption coefficient (α) depends on the density of states in the bands. If states at direct gap are dispersive it can lead to slowly increasing α resulting in significant absorption onset. Based on optical properties calculated for SnZrSe₃, $\alpha > 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is reached for photon energy $> 1.5 \text{ eV}$ which renders an onset of around 0.9 eV ¹⁸. Another theoretical work also shows that among ABX₃ chalcogenides those in needle-like phase have a larger absorption onset than those in perovskite structure¹², and this was measured for SrZrS₃ case experimentally [R1]. On the other hand, in materials with dispersive bands, a high carrier mobility can be expected. Consequently, for practical application, for instance solar cells, an optimum absorber thickness will be required to balance between charge carrier mobility, lifetime and absorption coefficient.

Reference: R1: <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201604733>

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 31 January 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.16407.r30579>

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Hao Zeng ¹ Department of Physics, University at Buffalo, Buffalo, NY, USA² Department of Physics, University at Buffalo, Buffalo, NY, USA

This paper reports the synthesis of chalcogenide perovskite SnZrSe₃, using solid state reaction. Very rarely has selenide perovskite been synthesized and their physical properties characterized. While the method used is not entirely novel, the results will be of great interest to the community working on chalcogenide perovskites. The paper is suitable for indexing after the authors address the following comments:

1. The authors stated that “However, other ABX₃ chalcogenides although having a non-perovskite ground phase, are also stable compounds, have bandgaps in the infrared region and have high optical absorption.” This is not entirely true. The hexagonal (indirect gap) and need-like phases (pseudo-direct gap) has weaker light absorption than that of the perovskite phase. See Sun’s Nano Lett paper (Ref. 12).
2. In this work, single phase perovskite was not achieved. Instead a mixture of binary phases including ZrSe₃, ZrSe₂ and SnSe were present. The authors should discuss if there is a pathway towards realizing phase pure materials. Without it the impact of the work is significantly limited.
3. It was shown that when the ampoule was oriented horizontally no secondary Sn-related phases were observed. What happens if excess Sn precursor is used? If there is no secondary phase, what happens to excess Sn?
4. It is stated that first-principles calculations are known to underestimate the bandgap. This is also not true. For example HSE predicted band gaps often are consistent with experimental results and GW sometimes tend to overestimate band gap.
5. It is stated that n-type samples are slightly more Se-rich. However, selenium vacancy should contribute to excess electron carriers. For Se-rich samples, where do excess electrons come from, if not from secondary phase or contaminations? Moreover, how does perovskite accommodate excess Se, unless they occupy cation sites? Such antisite defects are shown to have too high formation energy. Moreover, composition analysis seems to show that the samples are Se deficient (< 60%).
6. Presence of oxygen can lead to apparently higher band gap measured from UV-vis spectroscopy. Can the authors rule out presence of oxygen as the source of their apparently larger band gap than expected?
7. The authors should be careful on claiming presence of both n- and p-type doping, unless they can be sure secondary phases/contaminations are irrelevant. If n- and p-type behavior is indeed attributed to SnZrSe₃, defects/dopants should be identified. Furthermore, while authors pointed out that chalcopyrites are often p-type due to Cu vacancies, they failed to mention that both n- and p-type behavior has already been realized in chalcogenide perovskite BaZrS₃ using gating. see Yu *et al*, Nano Energy, 85, 105959¹.
8. The authors stated that “SnZrSe₃ is predicted to have a small (< 0.1 eV) difference between indirect and direct gaps as well. Such characteristic is highly desired in absorber materials

for photovoltaics because high absorption coefficient and long carrier lifetime can be realised simultaneously". Does the theory paper they cited and their own measurement results support this statement? In ref 18, it showed that the onset of absorption is at least .5 eV higher than the predicted band gap. Their own measurements also showed that significant absorption is only available at > 1.5 eV. What is the nature of the direct and indirect gap states? If the direct gap states are dispersive, they will not have high absorption. The authors should put this into perspective by comparing to existing materials (either the calculated dielectric constant or measured absorption coefficient).

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Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Chalcogenide perovskites, optoelectronic properties.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 18 May 2023

Rokas Kondrotas

Reviewer #1 This paper reports the synthesis of chalcogenide perovskite SnZrSe₃, using solid state reaction. Very rarely has selenide perovskite been synthesized and their physical properties characterized. While the method used is not entirely novel, the results will be of

great interest to the community working on chalcogenide perovskites.

Authors: first of all, we thank reviewers for on point comments and raised questions. In the following report we have addressed these questions as accurate as possible and updated the publication as provided herein.

Reviewer: The paper is suitable for indexing after the authors address the following comments:

The authors stated that “However, other ABX₃ chalcogenides although having a non-perovskite ground phase, are also stable compounds, have bandgaps in the infrared region and have high optical absorption.” This is not entirely true. The hexagonal (indirect gap) and needle-like phases (pseudo-direct gap) has weaker light absorption than that of the perovskite phase. See Sun’s Nano Lett paper (Ref. 12).

Authors: We do agree with a comment made. To avoid ambiguity and present potential drawbacks having a non-perovskite type ABX₃ materials, we modified this part of introduction as follows: Other ABX₃ chalcogenides although in a non-perovskite ground phase have bandgaps spanning from near to mid-wavelength infrared regions¹². Additionally, because valence and conduction bands in edge(face)-sharing ABX₃ chalcogenides is primarily determined by p and d orbitals of X and B elements, respectively, the absorption coefficient is expected to be high as well [R1.1]. Note, however, that lower symmetry crystal structures such as needle-like or BiNiO₃-type can lead to indirect optical transitions and therefore higher absorption onset as compared with ABX₃ chalcogenides in perovskite-type structure. Reference: R1.1. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.8b01038>

Reviewer: In this work, single phase perovskite was not achieved. Instead a mixture of binary phases including ZrSe₃, ZrSe₂ and SnSe were present. The authors should discuss if there is a pathway towards realizing phase pure materials. Without it the impact of the work is significantly limited.

Authors: when working with this material, indeed we were not able to achieve high yield of SnZrSe₃ phase. Traditionally, in a solid-state synthesis one focuses on finding optimal temperature and ensuring that precursors are evenly distributed through regrinding and mixing steps. Meanwhile duration of the annealing process was not taken into account having a perception that the longer process - the better. While continuing our work on the synthesis optimisation we noticed an interesting feature. Samples that were annealed for a shorter duration had higher yield of SnZrSe₃ phase. So we made additional experiments where only duration process was varied and found that shorter durations than we typically used for our process yielded a higher concentration of SnZrSe₃ phase. Having these new insights in the experiment we have updated the publication as follows: *-Slightly corrected the experimental section to include new annealing parameters:* Ampoules were introduced in the tube furnace, 13 of them in a horizontal and 3 of them in a vertical (placed in ceramic holder) positions at the centre of the heating zone. The heating process included either one or two steps: (i) temperature was raised to the top temperature within 3 – 7 h which was varied in the 600 – 800 °C range and held for 10 – 80 h; (ii) in the second step, the temperature was reduced to 100 – 600 °C within 7 – 60 h, and furnace power was switched

off leaving to cool down naturally for a few hours. We found that larger crystals were formed when the temperature was reduced slowly in the second stage, instead of maintaining a high furnace temperature for a prolonged period of time. Note: initially we presented that annealing at top temperature was held for 10 – 80 h, which suggests that we tested short annealing durations. However, a short duration was used in two-step annealing process where in the second step temperature was slowly (~ 0.03 °C/min) reduced. Therefore, technically duration at the crystallization temperature range was 60 – 80 h. - *Rewritten first paragraph about solid state synthesis as follows:* SnZrSe₃ was synthesized via solid state reaction from precursors in elemental form. Unless stated otherwise, a transport agent (SnI₂) was used to accelerate the reaction and to grow single crystals. In other cases, no additives were introduced. In most of experiments, various shapes, sizes and forms of crystals were present inside an ampoule after annealing indicating formation of secondary phases. By analysing XRD data we found that in addition to SnZrSe₃ phase, one or two of the following binary phases were present: ZrSe₃ (ICDD# 03-065-2351), ZrSe₂ (ICDD# 04-005-5128) and SnSe (ICDD# 04-009-2257). Based on multiple trials, we noticed that the following experimental parameters had a deciding factor on the phase composition: (i) spatial separation of precursor materials (ii) Se overpressure in the ampoule and (iii) annealing duration. When the ampoule was oriented vertically in the annealing zone, ZrSe₃ and traces of SnSe phases were present despite the annealing temperature applied (Figure 1a). Interestingly, the addition of transport agent in a form of SnI₂ did not change the phase composition. This suggested that when precursors were in close proximity, the solid-state reaction was not accelerated or favoured for the formation of SnZrSe₃ in the presence of a transport agent. When ampoules were oriented horizontally and precursor powder was spread over a certain length, phase composition strongly depended on the initial Se content. Using Se-deficient precursor, a large amount of ZrSe₂ and absence of ZrSe₃ phases were observed in the powder (Figure 1b). Once stoichiometric or Se-rich precursors were used, little to no amount of ZrSe₂ was found, which indicated that the formation of ZrSe₃ phase was highly favoured under Se-rich atmosphere. Note that when the ampoules were oriented horizontally no secondary Sn-related phases were observed. Finally, the annealing duration at the top temperature had a significant effect on SnZrSe₃ powder phase purity. In the initial experiments we used long annealing durations to facilitate a complete solid-state reaction. However, we noticed that shorter annealing durations yielded lower concentration of secondary phases (Figure 1 c). In the samples annealed under identical conditions but with different durations, we found that almost pure-phase powder was obtained annealing for 35 h instead of 60 h or more used previously (Figure 1c). Longer or shorter than 35 h annealing durations resulted in the formation of ZrSe₂ phase which concentration was much higher in the sample synthesized for a long period of time. This suggested that SnZrSe₃ formed relatively quickly and under prolonged annealing time slowly decomposed into binary phases. Therefore, from these results we can infer that 700 °C is close to the decomposition temperature of SnZrSe₃. - *Modified final paragraph about solid-state:* Therefore, we believe that the thermodynamic balance between reactions (3) and (4) which depends on spatial separation of materials, partial Se pressure and annealing temperature determine the final product composition. While inspecting the ampoule annealed sequentially first at 700 °C and then at 800 °C, it was noticed that after the second annealing large SnZrSe₃ crystals deteriorated, and small fine needle-like crystals typical for ZrSe₃ were found (Figure S1 in Extended data²²). This indicated that SnZrSe₃ decomposes at higher temperatures. This observation was in agreement with the results obtained from time-

dependent annealing series, where prolonged synthesis duration at 700 °C led to decomposition of SnZrSe₃. Therefore, to synthesize SnZrSe₃ phase with high yield, it is essential to keep balance between top temperature and annealing duration. With our experimental setup it was around 35 h at 700 °C. However, if lower temperature is applied, longer duration may be required and vice versa.

Updated Figure 1 by adding powder patterns of samples synthesized for different annealing durations: Figure 1. (a) Diffractograms of SnZrSe₃ powder synthesized at various temperatures in a vertical position without and with transport agent. (b) Diffractograms of SnZrSe₃ powder samples synthesized in the same experiment at 740 °C temperature in a horizontal position with different initial Se-content in the precursor as indicated in the graph. (c) Diffractograms of SnZrSe₃ powder annealed for different durations. Top temperature – 700 °C, SnI₂ transport agent, position – horizontal, composition – stoichiometric. (d) XRD pattern of collected and grinded crystals synthesized at 700 °C in horizontal position with a transport agent. Diffractogram of pure SnZrSe₃ phase was simulated using CIF file (underlying data²²).

Reviewer: In It was shown that when the ampoule was oriented horizontally no secondary Sn-related phases were observed. What happens if excess Sn precursor is used? If there is no secondary phase, what happens to excess Sn?

Authors: that is a valid point which we were asking ourselves too. Naturally, if we have a decomposition or incomplete reaction of binary phases we should be able to observe both Zr-related and Sn-related secondary phases. This, however, was not always the case. We are not entirely certain about the mechanism, but a current hypothesis is as follows: Sn-related phases were not observed in samples when horizontal configuration was used or higher than 700 °C temperature applied. In these ampoules, at the very end of ampoule (photo below), optically we observed condensation of material which had a mixture of metallic and red lustre. Usually, this part material was not collected for analysis because of difficulty to scratch it off from uneven quartz ends and was assumed to be condensate of transport agent. However, in few samples we have carried out chemical analysis of these droplets and found elements Sn, Se and I. This suggested that not only transport agent but also some Sn-Se phase condensed on ampoules ends. At high temperature (> 700 °C) all SnSe whether as a product of decomposition or incomplete reaction is likely in vapour phase and with a help of iodine is transferred to the coldest part of ampoule. Very likely this occurred during cool down step. So our primary explanation is that excess of Sn condensed on the very ends of ampoules and was not collected (Figure 2).

Reviewer: It is stated that first-principles calculations are known to underestimate the bandgap. This is also not true. For example HSE predicted band gaps often are consistent with experimental results and GW sometimes tend to overestimate band gap.

Authors: we do agree with reviewer's comment on the first principal high accuracy in predicting bandgap using hybrid functionals such as HSE06. The discrepancy we found in experimentally measured bandgap and the one calculated using mBJ (potential that also produces bandgaps consistent with experiments) was quite large i. e. 1.1 eV (exp) vs 0.53 eV (calc). We could argue that our experimental way of defining bandgap (using diffuse

reflectance) could potentially not account for weak indirect optical transitions, and that real indirect bandgap would be within error of calculated value. But based on the band structure the difference between direct and indirect gaps in SnZrSe_3 and SnZrS_3 is < 0.1 eV [T7]. This therefore cannot account for a large difference (> 0.5 eV) between experimental and calculated values. Note that this discrepancy is more pronounced for needle-like ABX_3 chalcogenides as shown in the Table 1 below. Based on this we conclude that needle-like phase ABX_3 chalcogenides are less accurately described in DFT than perovskite or hexagonal phases. Additionally, in SnZrSe_3 there exist a lone electron pair of Sn, which can further complicate high accuracy simulations using DFT.

Table 1. Bandgaps of selected ABX_3 chalcogenides determined experimentally and calculated using first principals. Compound Structure Exp E_g , eV Calc* E_g , eV ΔE_g , eV Ref. SrZrS_3 DP 2.13 1.95 0.18 [T1] SrZrS_3 N 1.53 1.17 **0.36** [T1] BaZrS_3 DP 1.81 1.75 0.06 [T1] BaTiS_3 H 0.27** 0.16 0.11 [T2] SrTiS_3 H 0.25** 0.25 0.0 [T3] SrHfS_3 DP 2.32 2.28 0.06 [T4] BaHfS_3 DP 2.06 2.0 0.06 [T4] SrHfSe_3 N 1.02 0.79 **0.24** [T5] SnZrSe_3 N 1.10 0.63 **0.47** This work DP – distorted perovskite structure, prototype GdFeO_3 N – needle-like structure, prototype NH_4CdCl_3 H – hexagonal structure, prototype BaNiO_3 * – all calculated values are taken from the work of Sun et al. [T6], except for SnZrSe_3 [T7]. Reference is provided for experimentally determined bandgap values. ** – absorption edge.

Taking the comments into account, we have modified the discussion part regarding calculated and observed bandgaps as follows: First-principles calculations using hybrid potentials can predict bandgaps consistent with experimental values therefore such large discrepancy we relate to one of the two reasons: (i) SnZrSe_3 is an indirect bandgap semiconductor and using diffuse reflectance method we were not able to clearly detect weak indirect optical transitions which would be expected to be lower in energy than direct (ii) due to low density of states at the band edges, strong optical absorption starts with a high onset leading significant absorption only at higher photon energies¹⁸.

References: T1. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201604733> T2. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41566-018-0189-1> T3. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.8b02279> T4. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.8b13622> T5. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.8b01038> T6. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl504046x> T7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtcomm.2021.102427>

Reviewer: It is stated that n-type samples are slightly more Se-rich. However, selenium vacancy should contribute to excess electron carriers. For Se-rich samples, where do excess electrons come from, if not from secondary phase or contaminations? Moreover, how does perovskite accommodate excess Se, unless they occupy cation sites? Such antisite defects are shown to have too high formation energy. Moreover, composition analysis seems to show that the samples are Se deficient ($< 60\%$).

Authors: first, we would like to clarify that when we used the term “more Se-rich” we meant Se content when comparing samples with each other, but not with expected ABX_3 stoichiometric composition 1:1:3. We have clarified this as follows: In both samples, the cationic ratio A/B was identical, whereas the n-type crystal was slightly more Se-rich than p-type, but both were Se-deficient with respect to stoichiometric ratio of $[X]/([A]+[B])$ which is

1.5. All samples which we have analysed can be considered as Se-deficient and cation-rich with respect to an ideal 1:1:3 ratio. In terms of atomic percentage of Se it was always found to be in 57 – 58.5 at.% range. If high oxygen contamination was present, even lower Se concentration was found. However, even for very clean as-grown crystals measured immediately after synthesis where no oxygen was present, the Se content was no more than 58.5 at.%. There are two possible reasons for this observation: (i) deviation could be related to the high measurement system error (> 2 at.%). Although this is unlikely because using the same conditions we measured the composition of GaAs, GeS, GeSe monocrystals on the same system and all them showed a 50:50 atomic ratio with 0.5 at.% error. Another reason could be that a equilibrium composition of SnZrSe₃ is not 1:1:3, but slightly cation-rich and anion-deficient such as: 1.05 : 1.05 : 2.9. In fact, other ABX₃ chalcogenides in needle-like or hexagonal phases were also found not to follow 1:1:3 ratio strictly, e. g. Ba_{1.12}Zr_{1.0}Se_{3.01}, Sr₂₁Ti₁₉Se₅₇ [R5.1] or Sn_{1.2}Ti_{0.8}S₃ [R5.2] Ba_{1.06}Ti₁S_{2.95} [R5.3]. Thus it is not known for certain what is the precise equilibrium stoichiometry of SnZrSe₃ compound and at which point it can be regarded as Se-rich or Se-poor. Therefore, in our work we focused on comparing and finding trends within sample series rather than with absolute values. Additionally, we have strong evidence that cations play more important role than anion in defect chemistry related to conductivity on which we elaborated more in question 7. Because of the reasons outlined above, the discussion about Se-vacancy defects as potential donors becomes speculative. Although we cannot completely rule out the contribution of V_{Se}, there is a stronger correlation of conductivity type and carrier concentration with cation composition.

References: R5.1. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja972442p> R5.2. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5093183> R5.3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41566-018-0189-1> (in supporting information)

Reviewer: Presence of oxygen can lead to apparently higher band gap measured from UV-vis spectroscopy. Can the authors rule out presence of oxygen as the source of their apparently larger band gap than expected?

Authors: we agree that oxygen if incorporated in the lattice and resulting in formation of SnZr(Se,O)₃ alloy would lead to higher than expected bandgap as was observed in [R6.1]. However, there are two reasons why we think oxygen had no contribution in optical absorption in our case: (i) first powder sample that were used to measure bandgap was obtained by grinding needle-shaped crystals. Compositional analysis of the crystals usually showed no content or very minor traces of oxygen. Higher content of oxygen was observed when crystals were grounded to powder and exposed for prolonged time under ambient. This shows that during synthesis process there was no contamination with oxygen, and it was not incorporated in the lattice. It is very unlikely that at room temperature oxygen from air would be incorporated into the crystal lattice of SnZrSe₃ and lead to formation of SnZr(Se,O)₃. (ii) Another evidence that oxygen does not enter SnZrSe₃ lattice is based on the lattice parameters of SnZrSe₃. If oxygen was incorporated in the crystal lattice, the lattice parameters of SnZrSe₃ would shrink because of much smaller ionic radius of O than Se. In the following Table 2 we present lattice parameters calculated for one of our SnZrSe₃ powder:

Table 2. Lattice constants of SnZrSe₃ Sample a, Å b, Å c, Å As synthesized 9.5940 3.8463

14.4087 Aged 7 months 9.5936 3.8462 14.4082 Single crystal 9.5862 3.8443 14.3959

It is quite clear that lattice constants do not change with time indicating there is no change in SnZrSe₃ lattice under ambient conditions, and that lattice parameters calculated for powder sample is slightly higher than measured in single crystal. If oxygen was incorporated in the lattice, there would be a much more significant shift of lattice constants and toward smaller not higher values. Reference: R6.1.

<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.1c00177>

Reviewer: The authors should be careful on claiming presence of both n- and p-type doping, unless they can be sure secondary phases/contaminations are irrelevant. If n- and p-type behavior is indeed attributed to SnZrSe₃, defects/dopants should be identified. Furthermore, while authors pointed out that chalcopyrites are often p-type due to Cu vacancies, they failed to mention that both n- and p-type behavior has already been realized in chalcogenide perovskite BaZrS₃ using gating. see Yu et al, Nano Energy, 85, 1059591.

Authors: we do agree that claims about n- and p-type doping engineering in SnZrSe₃ based on intrinsic defects lack more evidence therefore we acknowledged a possible contribution of impurities in the following part: "Important to note that since iodine was used as a transport agent to facilitate the solid state reaction during synthesis, it could be inadvertently introduced in the lattice giving rise to extrinsic doping. Iodine could not be detected by EDX, but we acknowledge that very small amounts (beyond the EDX detection limit) can have a significant contribution to the conductivity behaviour." Because single crystals were used for electrical measurements, we are quite certain that there is no contribution to conductivity from secondary phases. Secondly, because we were able to observe p-type conductivity, we can be sure, that p-type can be achieved to some extent by modifying SnZrSe₃ composition alone. Finally, although extrinsic doping via iodine impurities is possible, in chalcogenides doping of halogens usually introduce shallow donor defects, e.g. ZnSe:I E_a = 0.026 eV [R7.2], SnS:Cl E_a=0.0015 eV [R7.3], Sb₂Se₃:Br E_a=0.06 eV (calculated) [R7.4]. Therefore, despite whichever sample we test, we should be able to observe additional probably low activation energy in the conductivity vs temperature graph. This was not the case. So we strongly believe that n- and p-type doping originated from intrinsic SnZrSe₃ defects. To identify which point defects are responsible for generating free electrons/holes is very difficult without knowledge of defect chemistry in SnZrSe₃ on theoretical basis. This is our initial work on SnZrSe₃ and in the future it would be extremely useful to analyse defect chemistry from first-principles. This then would allow us to identify potential free carrier generating defects. Additionally, currently we are working of the synthesis of Sn(Zr_{1-x}Ti_x)Se₃ alloy system and observed a very strong correlation between change of resistivity (5 orders of magnitude) and Ti content which again points to the fact that cations rather than anion or extrinsic doping is more critical to electrical behaviour of SnZrSe₃. Regarding the achievements in observing both type carriers in BaZrS₃, this is indeed an important milestone and this publication was added in the main text: In this work, we found that SnZrSe₃ showed p as well as n type conductivity behaviour. Ambipolar behaviour was also recently realised in BaZrS₃ thin films [R7.1].

Reference R7.1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2021.105959> R7.2.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0248\(88\)90607-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0248(88)90607-0) R7.3.

<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.cgd.0c00617> R7.4. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsaem.9b02192>

Reviewer: The authors stated that “SnZrSe₃ is predicted to have a small (< 0.1 eV) difference between indirect and direct gaps as well. Such characteristic is highly desired in absorber materials for photovoltaics because high absorption coefficient and long carrier lifetime can be realised simultaneously”. Does the theory paper they cited and their own measurement results support this statement? In ref 18, it showed that the onset of absorption is at least .5 eV higher than the predicted band gap. Their own measurements also showed that significant absorption is only available at > 1.5 eV. What is the nature of the direct and indirect gap states? If the direct gap states are dispersive, they will not have high absorption. The authors should put this into perspective by comparing to existing materials (either the calculated dielectric constant or measured absorption coefficient).

Authors: Regarding the first question, we do not have estimates of carrier lifetime therefore we cannot fully support the statement. Whether bands are dispersive we can only rely on ref 18 results, which suggest that it strongly depends on the crystallographic direction. Near the indirect gap region bands are indeed flat which would suggest high optical absorption, whereas in other directions they are dispersive, e.g. $\Gamma \rightarrow R$ (figure below). Note that in ref 18 only the calculated values of absorption coefficient are presented. However, we do acknowledge that larger absorption onset was observed in ABX₃ chalcogenides of needle-like phase and therefore extend the discussion in the manuscript as follows: On one hand, absorption coefficient (α) depends on the density of states in the bands. If states at direct gap are dispersive it can lead to slowly increasing α resulting in significant absorption onset. Based on optical properties calculated for SnZrSe₃, $\alpha > 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is reached for photon energy > 1.5 eV which renders an onset of around 0.9 eV¹⁸. Another theoretical work also shows that among ABX₃ chalcogenides those in needle-like phase have a larger absorption onset than those in perovskite structure¹², and this was measured for SrZrS₃ case experimentally [R8.1]. On the other hand, in materials with dispersive bands, a high carrier mobility can be expected. Consequently, for practical application, for instance solar cells, an optimum absorber thickness will be required to balance between charge carrier mobility, lifetime and absorption coefficient.

Electronic band dispersion curves of SnZrSe₃ along high symmetry direction of the Brillouin zone. Adapted from ref.18. Reference: R8.1: <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201604733>

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.